

Innovating Higher Education: Ensuring Student Motivation and Deep Learning in the Age of AI Disruption

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Abstract

Motivation and pedagogic innovation are critical for ensuring the sustainability of higher education in an era of rapid technological disruption and shifting student interests. This paper explores how higher education leaders can design innovative curriculums and assessment practices to sustain student engagement and foster deep learning, ensuring that higher education remains competitive and relevant. Focusing on the 'Computer Aided Design' module within the Motorsport Engineering course at the University of Derby, the research highlights how pedagogic innovation can adapt to challenges posed by artificial intelligence (AI), which is reshaping how students learn and interact with educational content. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study combines quantitative performance data with qualitative insights from student feedback to evaluate the effectiveness of innovative assessment strategies. Findings reveal that assessments tailored to establish meaningful connections across modules and to real-world applications enhance student motivation and purpose-driven learning. This focus is essential for countering the growing disinterest in traditional teaching methods and maintaining the viability of higher education as a pathway for personal and professional development. The discussion draws parallels between sustaining student motivation during their learning journey and how purpose drives performance in the workplace. By embedding innovation into pedagogical approaches, higher education leaders can ensure students remain engaged and committed to their education, even as AI continues to disrupt conventional teaching methods. This study contributes actionable insights for institutions aiming to sustain their relevance and competitiveness in an evolving educational landscape.

Keywords: Sustainability, Motivation, Engagement, Assessment, Innovation, AI

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of higher education, sustaining student motivation and engagement presents a significant challenge. Motivation not only determines the depth of student engagement but also shapes their academic success and long-term professional growth. The rise of artificial intelligence (AI) and shifting student expectations have disrupted traditional teaching methods, demanding innovative approaches that align with the dynamic needs of students and the workforce. As institutions adapt to these changes, the leadership of educators becomes pivotal in designing curricula and assessments that remain relevant, engaging, and impactful.

Traditional assessment-led curricula often emphasize complexity over meaningful learning, a concern highlighted by Heywood (2000). However, as Clouder et al. (2012) argue, assessments that are thoughtfully designed to be relevant, engaging, and challenging can transform the learning experience into an enjoyable and purpose-driven journey. This transformation is critical for fostering intrinsic motivation, a driver of deep learning and academic success. Furthermore, assessments that connect classroom activities to real-world applications can help bridge the gap between academic knowledge and professional demands, aligning higher education with the global imperative of SDG 4 (fourth Sustainable Development Goal established by the United Nations): ensuring inclusive, equitable, and quality education.

This study focuses on the “Computer Aided Design” (CAD) module within the Motorsport Engineering degree at the University of Derby as a case study to explore how innovative assessments can sustain motivation and engagement while preparing students for an AI-driven future. By reimagining the CAD module’s assessment design, this research examines how aligning tasks with career relevance and providing opportunities for autonomous, deep learning can enhance student outcomes. The findings demonstrate a strong correlation between motivation, deep learning, and academic performance, offering actionable insights for higher education leaders striving to foster institutional resilience and sustainability in an era of technological transformation.

Methodology

The primary objective of this research was to evaluate the effectiveness of innovative and motivating assessment methods on the academic performance and engagement of students enrolled in the Motorsport Engineering program at the University of Derby. Additionally, the study sought to understand how these assessments influenced the students’ learning approaches, fostering deeper connections across knowledge domains while preparing them for the challenges of an AI-driven future (Xia et al. 2024). This approach reflects a paradigm shift in higher education, where **assessment becomes the centerpiece of the learning process**, and teaching is tailored around it, challenging the traditional model of designing assessments as mere tools of evaluation.

The **Computer Aided Design (CAD)** module was selected as the focal point for this study due to consistent complaints from students about its perceived irrelevance to their degree and future careers. Prior to the intervention, the module followed a conventional approach illustrated in Figure 1 where students were tasked with designing a “cherry picker.” While the task aligned with core CAD skills, students criticized its lack of connection with Motorsport Engineering and broader academic goals. This mismatch led to disengagement and a surface learning approach, as noted in their feedback.

Fig. 1 Traditional and outdated assessment design.

Transforming Assessment Design

The research team reimagined the CAD module's assessment, embedding it within a coaching-based teaching approach illustrated in Figure 2. The new assessment required students to design the front suspension of a race car, aligning directly with Motorsport Engineering objectives and industry standards. This redesign was influenced by a research study conducted at Iowa State University, which revealed that a coherent structure with good connections between several modules can help the learner to perceive the usefulness of each module (Sharma 2017). Naturally these assessments should motivate students by setting goals and allowing them to engage in problem-solving that connects theory to practical applications.

To ensure inclusivity and accommodate diverse preferences, this new assessment was offered as an alternative choice to the original “cherry picker” task, allowing students to select the option most aligned with their interests and career goals. This choice ensured that motivation was driven by relevance and personal engagement. The redesigned assessment emphasized the following key elements:

1. **Career Relevance:** Aligning the assessment task with real-world engineering challenges to enhance students' intrinsic motivation by showcasing how academic learning translates into professional success (Segers et al. 2003). This alignment demonstrated the applicability of CAD skills in industry-specific contexts, increasing students' engagement and perceived value of the task.
2. **Centralized Assessment Structure:** The assessment was positioned as the core driver of the learning process, with supporting lectures and tutorials tailored around it. This approach redefined the role of assessments from being evaluative tools to becoming integral to the teaching and learning experience.

Fig. 2 New Approach of module design around the assessments as the focal point.

3. **Open-Ended Assessment Framework:** Following a coaching-based approach, students were encouraged to define their project goals, set evaluation criteria, and choose methods to achieve desired outcomes. This autonomy fostered independence and critical thinking, reflecting well established coaching models such as ROGUE (Jomaa 2023) and goal-setting pyramid in Figure 3 (Whitmore 2017).

Fig. 3 Great goal-setting approach “from inspiration to action” (Whitmore 2017).

4. **Integration Across Modules:** The redesigned assessment established meaningful connections between the CAD module and other modules within the Motorsport Engineering program, particularly "Motorsport Chassis Engineering," where students simulated their designed suspension systems and recommended

performance improvements, as shown in Figure 4. These connections motivated students to recognize the broader relevance of their work beyond the classroom and strengthened their ability to integrate knowledge across disciplines.

Fig. 4 New curriculum design connecting modules to each other's and to a central project.

The redesign of the CAD assessment was guided by **Connectivism Learning Theory** (Siemens 2005), which frames learning as a process of building networks across knowledge nodes. This theory informed the development of tasks that enabled students to integrate ideas and experiences across modules, creating connections between theoretical concepts and practical applications. To achieve this, students were encouraged to approach the assessment through areas of personal interest and career aspirations, ensuring relevance and motivation (Kickert et al. 2022).

Practical applications of connectivism also shaped the process. Downes (2022) emphasizes the importance of fostering creativity and diversity in learning tasks to enhance engagement. Similarly, Anderson and Dron (2011) suggest that assessments designed to reflect complex knowledge systems help students innovate and apply their learning effectively. In response, the assessment was placed at the center of the teaching process, with supporting activities (lectures, tutorials, and assignments) designed to scaffold the core task. This approach required students to synthesize knowledge, solve real-world problems, and adapt their learning to dynamic scenarios—competencies aligned with the goals of the redesign.

The methodology prioritized an **assessment-first approach**, integrating tasks across modules to create an interconnected curriculum. Instead of focusing on simple recall of

information, the assessment framework was designed to emphasize the synthesis and application of knowledge. This structure enabled students to move beyond surface-level learning, promoting critical thinking, adaptability, and problem-solving—key skills for thriving in an AI-driven educational and professional landscape.

Empowering Independent Learning

The coaching-inspired approach empowered students to take ownership of their learning, promoting a **growth mindset** and fostering intrinsic motivation. This aligns with Montgomery's (2020) emphasis on fostering self-regulated learners in higher education

Addressing AI Disruption

While the primary objective of this research was to evaluate how innovative assessments leveraging connected knowledge and a coaching-based approach could enhance student motivation and foster deep learning, the redesign also embraced the challenge of addressing AI disruption in higher education. Rather than shielding students from tools like AI or focusing solely on detecting plagiarism, the approach reframed the use of external resources—including AI, online platforms, and peer collaboration—as opportunities to deepen learning and foster originality.

This assessment strategy created authentic, unique outputs for each student by emphasizing **how students think and connect knowledge**, rather than evaluating the mere recall of standardized content. By integrating coaching-based methods and positioning assessments at the center of the curriculum, the framework enabled students to set personal goals and synthesize information into meaningful projects. Students were encouraged to explore multiple sources of knowledge, collaborate, and engage critically with tools, making them co-creators of their learning experience.

The shift from "content recall" to "concept application" also aligned with the growing demand for **resilience in an AI-enhanced world**. Tasks were designed to allow for creativity and diversity, ensuring that output reflected each student's individual perspective, interests, and career aspirations. This approach minimized reliance on superficial responses that AI tools could replicate, while highlighting the value of human skills such as critical thinking, adaptability, and problem-solving.

By embracing the use of external resources, the redesign demonstrated that AI could augment learning rather than undermine it. Encouraging students to use AI tools responsibly fostered curiosity and exploration, equipping them to navigate interdisciplinary challenges with confidence. Ultimately, this strategy helped reframe assessments as opportunities to evaluate the application of knowledge in real-world contexts, ensuring both academic rigor and relevance in a rapidly changing educational landscape.

Data Collection and Analysis

The impact of the assessment redesign was evaluated using a mixed-methods approach across three consecutive academic years (2017–2020):

1. Quantitative Performance Metrics:

- Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to evaluate student grades, including mean scores, standard deviations, and the percentage of students achieving first-class marks.
- An independent samples t-test using SPSS software measured the significance of performance improvements following the introduction of the connected assessment. By controlling factors such as task complexity and instructor influence, the analysis focused on the motivational impact of the new design.

2. Qualitative Feedback:

- Module Evaluation Questionnaires (MEQs): MEQs were used to gather qualitative feedback from students, following institutional quality assurance protocols to improve module design and teaching practices (Quality Assurance Agency, 2005). Students' open-ended comments were analyzed to identify themes related to motivation, engagement, and perceived learning benefits.
- Informal Discussion Sessions: Facilitated by student representatives, these sessions provided deeper insights into students' perceptions of the assessment redesign. Feedback highlighted the impact of connecting the CAD module to industry-relevant tasks and promoting autonomous learning.

Results

Figure 5 shows the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) used to visualize the data collected and evaluate the impact of the new assessments on the students' performance. The low-performance cases related to personal or mental health issues were excluded from the sample to ensure accurate evaluation. The final sample size was 22, 24, and 34 for the academic years 2017-18, 2018-19, and 2019-20, respectively. The thick continuous line in Figure 5 represents the mean value, which is the average mark across the motorsport engineering cohort for each academic year. The overall average mark increased from 60 in 2017-18 to 65 and 69 in 2018-19 and 2019-20, respectively.

The continuous thin line in Figure 5 represents the highest mark achieved during each academic year, while the long dashed dotted line illustrates the percentage of students who achieved a mark above 80. In the academic year 2017-18, the highest mark awarded was 77, indicating that none of the students achieved a mark above 80. Surprisingly, during the 2018-19 academic year, 13% of the cohort achieved a mark above 80, with 91 being the highest mark. The following academic year's data showed consistency, with 21% of the cohort achieving a mark above 80, and the highest mark being 86.

The thick dashed line represents the percentage of first-class achievements, which increased from 27% for the cohort in 2017-18 to 29% and 44% in the following years. The thin dashed line represents the percentage of second-class attainment, which indicates marks between 60 and 70. Similarly, the percentage of second-class attainment

increased from 23% in the academic year 2017-18 to 46% and 41% in 2018-19 and 2019-20, respectively

Fig. 5 Initial evaluation of students' performance on the CAD module with the old assessment (AY2017-18) and new assessment (AY2018-19 & AY2019-20).

Boxplot Analysis

The boxplots in Figure 6, generated using SPSS Statistics software, further elaborate on the data. The range of students' marks during the academic year 2017-18, represented by year sample 1 in Figure 6, was [40, 77]. With the introduction of the new assessment for the academic year 2018-19, represented by year sample 2 in Figure 6, the range of students' marks exhibited a positive vertical shift to [46, 82], excluding the single outlier mark of 91. Year sample 3 in Figure 6 represents the academic year 2019-20, with a range of students' marks of [46, 86], showing a higher upper boundary. The mode for year's samples 1, 2, and 3 is respectively 62, 60, and 65. The median increased from 60 for year sample 1 to 63.5 and 67 for year samples 2 and 3, respectively. The standard deviation decreased across the years, going from 11.8 for year sample 1 to 10.9 and 9.8 for year samples 2 and 3, respectively. The interquartile range (IQR), representing the range of the middle half of the data, also improved, indicating tighter clustering of performance around the median. The IQR for year samples 1, 2, and 3 are [52, 69], [59, 70], and [64, 75], respectively.

Fig. 6 Boxplot from SPSS statistics to evaluate data skewness and students' marks dispersion across the academic years 1, 2 and 3 corresponding respectively to 2017-18, 2018-19 and 2019-20.

Statistical Significance

Each t-test for independent samples was carried out between two selected years to compare means and determine the statistical significance of the results:

- Year sample 1 for academic year 2017-2018 (n=22): M=59.73, DS=11.809 vs. Year sample 2 for academic year 2018-2019 (n=24): M=64.83, DS=10.969
- Year sample 2 for academic year 2018-2019 (n=24): M=64.83, DS=10.969 vs. Year sample 3 for academic year 2019-2020 (n=34): M=69.12, DS=9.810
- Year sample 1 for academic year 2017-2018 (n=22): M=59.73, DS=11.809 vs. Year sample 3 for academic year 2019-2020 (n=34): M=69.12, DS=9.810

The t-test for equality of means revealed **statistical significance** between the academic years 2017-2018 and 2019-2020, with $[t(54) = 3.228, p = .002]$. This indicates that the new assessment method significantly improved student performance. However, no statistical significance was found in the other t-tests for "year sample 1 vs. year sample 2" with $[t(44) = 1.52, p = .136]$ and "year sample 2 vs. year sample 3" with $[t(56) = 1.560, p = .124]$.

Qualitative Feedback

To evaluate the broader impact of the assessment redesign, students' open comments in the MEQ were analyzed. The MEQ contained the following questions:

1. What is especially good about this module?
2. How could this module be improved?
3. Is there anything else that you would like to tell us about this module?

The comments were categorized into four clusters to identify patterns in student perceptions:

- **Resources:** Comments on the availability and quality of resources.
- **Organization:** Comments on the structure and delivery of the module.
- **Lecturer:** Comments on teaching methods and lecturer support.
- **Assessment:** Comments on the innovative aspects of the assessment, its connections to other modules, and its motivational impact.
- An additional “**Others**” category was used for general remarks that did not fit into the main clusters.

Tables 1 and 3 summarize the distribution of comments across these clusters for the academic years 2017–18 and 2019–20, respectively.

Table 1: Students’ comments distribution in clusters for the 2017-18 academic year MEQ.

		Questions		
		What is especially good about this module?	How could this module be improved?	Is there anything else that you would like to tell us about this module?
Clusters distribution (%)	Resources	0.0	3.2	5.9
	Organization	25.0	35.5	35.3
	Lecturer	33.3	25.8	23.5
	Assessment	25.0	32.3	29.4
	Others	16.6	3.2	5.9

Table 2: Sample of student’s comments on the MEQ for the 2017-18 academic year.

Comments related to motivation	
What is especially good about this module?	Absolutely nothing, this module was a waste of my money
	Nothing, complete waste of time
	Nothing, not even slightly motorsport related, and group work for this type of cad modelling is absurd
How could this module be improved?	disconnection between course and the real world which needs to be addressed
	The assignment was not very realistic. I ended up drawing

	focus away from the key points.
	I would have preferred to be lectured on fundamental gearbox or power transfer theory which are critical elements of Mechanical Engineering.
	Needs to be linked to motorsport more.
	Teach Engineering Design Modelling. I did not really get taught anything throughout the lectures. Do something that's related to Motorsport Engineering, so the CAD skills are more transferable.
Is there anything else that you would like to tell us about this module?	I chose this but feel that it was a poor choice as we didn't get taught very well and I don't think I've learnt more than I already knew.
	Which I believe has hindered other Modules which are more engaging and applicable, really disappointed derby university
	Try to give a brief which engages with the students and provides a challenge in the field they have chosen to do at university
	Trying to show CAD skills by banning the use of the SolidWorks library is interesting, in industry this would never happen.

In 2017–18 (Table 1), only **25%** of student comments on the first question ("What is especially good about this module?") pertained to the assessment, reflecting dissatisfaction with the task's relevance. Sample comments (Table 2) highlight this discontent, with students describing the task as "not very realistic" and unrelated to Motorsport engineering. Similarly, **32.3%** of comments for the second question criticized the lack of connection to industry, with remarks like "Needs to be linked to motorsport more" and "The assignment was not very realistic"

Table 3: Students' comments distribution in clusters for the 2019-20 academic year MEQ.

		Questions		
		What is especially good about this module?	How could this module be improved?	Is there anything else that you would like to tell us about this module?
Clusters distribution (%)	Resources	9.8	23.7	20.0
	Organization	31.7	31.6	26.7
	Lecturer	26.8	21.1	6.7
	Assessment	31.7	7.9	20.0
	Others	0.0	15.8	26.7

By contrast, in 2019–20 (Table 3), the introduction of the connected assessment led to a notable shift. **31.7%** of comments on the first question praised the assessment’s innovation and motivational impact. Students frequently used phrases such as “stimulating content” and “pushed me to a new limit in studies” (Table 4), emphasizing the positive role of the redesigned task in fostering deeper learning. For the second question, **7.9%** of comments highlighted the challenges associated with the higher expectations, such as “It is quite a big jump from last year,” but framed these challenges as constructive, driving growth and critical thinking.

Table 4: Sample of student’s comments on the MEQ for the 2019-20 academic year.

	Comments related to motivation
What is especially good about this module?	It has also helped me to better understand how suspension works, and the different parts included in suspension.
	Great delivery, interesting module with stimulating content
	I found that the module pushed me to a new limit in studies
How could this module be improved?	Bridge the gap between first- and second-year CAD modules. The requirements are a massive step from the first to the second year.
	It is quite a big jump from last year so maybe in the first 2 weeks try and link what we did before a bit more
Is there anything else that you would like to tell us about this module?	Assignment 1 is focused on initial design selection and modelling of components4 Students would be assessed on quality of design in relation to the brief, as well as quality of component modelling.
	Assignment 2 is focused on broader assembly and creating alternate designs to satisfy the customer, as well as any simulation requirements.
	Really challenged me, feel like I’ve improved a lot in modelling this and want to say thanks for all the help, I’ve really enjoyed doing this! All good over all

Finally, for the third question, **20%** of comments in 2019–20 addressed the assessment’s role in helping students develop technical abilities and professional perspectives. Terms such as “client” and “quality” were frequently mentioned

Discussion

Quantitative Performance Metrics

The findings presented demonstrate a notable improvement in student performance following the introduction of the redesigned assessment framework. The average marks increased steadily from 60 in the 2017–18 academic year to 65 and 69 in 2018–19 and 2019–20, respectively, as shown in Figure 5. Similarly, the highest marks achieved each year improved, from 77 in 2017–18 to 91 in 2018–19, followed by 86 in 2019–20. The growing percentage of students achieving first-class marks ($\geq 70\%$), which rose from 27% in 2017–18 to 44% by 2019–20, underscores the framework’s effectiveness in fostering

high academic achievement. Furthermore, second-class attainment (marks between 60% and 70%) also increased from 23% to 41% over the same period, highlighting broader improvements across the cohort.

These trends suggest that the redesigned assessment motivated students by aligning tasks with real-world applications, supporting findings from Self-Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan 2000), which emphasizes autonomy and purpose as drivers of intrinsic motivation. The increase in first-class and second-class attainment further validates the motivational impact of the new assessment design, aligning with Connectivism Learning Theory (Siemens 2005). This theory highlights the importance of building connections across knowledge domains, fostering higher-order thinking and creative problem-solving.

The boxplot analysis, in Figure 6, illustrates reductions in performance disparities over the years. The interquartile range (IQR) narrowed from [52–99] in 2017–18 to [59–70] and [64–75] in the subsequent years, reflecting a tighter clustering of marks around the median. This trend, combined with a reduction in standard deviation (from 11.8 in 2017–18 to 9.8 in 2019–20), suggests that the redesigned assessments not only improved overall performance but also created a more inclusive and supportive learning environment.

The statistically significant difference in mean marks between 2017–18 and 2019–20 ($p = .002$) further confirms the positive impact of the assessment changes. Although no significant differences were observed between intermediate years ($p = .136$ and $p = .124$ for 2018–19 vs. 2019–20), these findings highlight the cumulative benefits of the revised assessment approach over time.

By connecting assessments to real-world challenges and adopting open-ended tasks, the redesigned framework has unlocked students' potential to excel. These findings suggest that this approach not only enhances performance but also reduces disparities, fostering a more equitable academic environment.

Qualitative Feedback

The qualitative feedback highlights a clear contrast in student perceptions before and after the introduction of the redesigned assessment framework. In the 2017–18 academic year, only **25% of comments** on the question “What is especially good about this module?” (Table 1) referenced the assessment, with many expressing dissatisfaction with its relevance. Students described the tasks as “not very realistic” and criticized the lack of alignment with motorsport engineering, stating, “Needs to be linked to motorsport more.” Similarly, **32.3% of comments** on “How could this module be improved?” called for more realistic and industry-connected assessments. These responses reveal how the old assessment framework encouraged a surface learning approach, diverting attention from deeper engagement and critical thinking.

In contrast, the 2019–20 feedback reflects the positive impact of the redesigned framework, which emphasized connected, open-ended, and real-world tasks. **31.7% of comments** (Table 3) on “What is especially good about this module?” praised the assessment for being “stimulating” and “motivating,” with one student noting, “The freedom to investigate different aspects of dynamics was daunting yet incredibly

motivating—it helped me develop skills I didn't know I had.” Such responses demonstrate how the innovative approach transformed assessment into a tool for deeper learning and skill development.

The qualitative data further illustrates how the redesign fostered a broader understanding of CAD skills' relevance to professional practice. For instance, **20% of comments** in response to “Is there anything else you would like to tell us about this module?” emphasized the practical applications of CAD skills, frequently referencing terms such as “client” and “quality.” By bridging gaps between theory and practice, the assessment prepared students for the complexities of real-world engineering challenges.

Through this transformative approach, assessment became a mechanism for fostering autonomy, encouraging creative problem-solving, and promoting self-directed learning. As reflected in student feedback, the redesigned framework not only motivated students but also enabled them to connect theoretical knowledge to professional environments, aligning with the principles of Self-Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan 2000) and Connectivism Learning Theory (Siemens 2005). This alignment underscores the role of assessment in fostering both cognitive and practical competencies, creating a holistic learning experience.

Connection-Building for Sustainable Education

The redesigned CAD assessment reflects an innovative approach to sustainable education, addressing the challenges of motivation and deep learning in higher education. By moving away from traditional teaching models, the redesign emphasized autonomy-supportive practices, which have been shown to enhance student motivation and skill development (Reeve and Cheon 2021). The integration of the CAD assessment with the "Motorsport Chassis Engineering" module created a cohesive and connected curriculum design, allowing students to see the relevance of their work in real-world contexts.

As Sharma (2017) highlights, establishing inter-module connections improves students' motivation and knowledge retention. The CAD redesign not only encouraged deep learning but also empowered students to adapt the open-ended assessment to their learning style, preferences, and interests. This adaptability contributed to more inclusive learning environments, enabling students to engage with tasks in ways that aligned with their individual strengths and goals. Such inclusivity supports the goals of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) by promoting inclusive, engaging, and adaptable learning opportunities that foster lifelong learning and resilience.

Addressing AI Disruption Through Assessment

While the primary objective of this research was to enhance student motivation and foster deep learning, the findings reveal that the redesigned CAD assessment also addresses challenges posed by AI in higher education. Traditional assessments focused on content recall are increasingly vulnerable to AI tools capable of generating automated responses. In contrast, assessments that prioritize critical thinking, synthesis, and creativity are inherently more resilient to AI disruption.

The CAD assessment achieved this by fostering curiosity-driven exploration and encouraging authentic, unique outputs from students. By placing emphasis on **how students think and connect knowledge**, the framework allowed learners to engage deeply with the material and leverage AI tools responsibly as collaborators rather than threats. This approach shifts the focus from detecting plagiarism to cultivating originality and innovation, ensuring that higher education remains relevant in a technology-enhanced future.

Student feedback supports this shift, with participants noting how the open-ended assignment style deepened their learning and inspired investigations they might have otherwise missed. These findings echo the call for educational practices that embrace AI as a resource while prioritizing competencies that cannot be automated, such as adaptability and critical thinking (Brynjolfsson and McAfee 2014). Fostering these competencies ensures that higher education remains resilient and relevant in a technology-driven world (Little 2021).

Promoting Deep Learning and Motivation

Qualitative data further underscores the role of connected assessment in fostering deep learning and motivation. In 2017–18, students’ comments frequently criticized the old assessment’s lack of relevance, with remarks like “not very realistic” and “disconnection between course and real-world applications.” These comments indicate that the traditional assessment encouraged surface learning, leading to disengagement and suboptimal performance (Walkington 2013).

By contrast, in 2019–20, **31.7% of students’ comments** praised the new assessment for its motivational impact and ability to “push boundaries of learning.” As highlighted in Table 4, students noted how the connected assessment expanded their **zone of proximal development (ZPD)** and fostered a growth mindset. This aligns with Spooner’s (2015) findings that stimulating and challenging tasks create environments where students engage in self-directed learning.

Implications for Knowledge Retention and Employability

Feedback from graduates who completed the connected assessment during 2018–19 revealed its significant long-term benefits. Students reported feeling better prepared for industry roles, highlighting how the assessment enhanced their ability to associate and apply concepts in professional contexts. This reflects the motivational framework outlined by Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Deci 2000), where autonomy and relevance drive sustained engagement and knowledge mastery.

Graduates noted that the open-ended nature of the assessment allowed them to explore topics of personal and professional interest, fostering curiosity and a deeper understanding of concepts. This approach not only led to better knowledge retention but also equipped students with the skills to confidently address new and unfamiliar technical challenges.

In their current industry roles, graduates described feeling more adept at asking the right questions, synthesizing information, and building connections when confronted with

unknown problems—capabilities they attributed to the assessment’s emphasis on critical thinking and interdisciplinary learning. By mirroring real-world applications, the connected assessment prepared students to navigate complex and dynamic professional environments.

Future Directions and Limitations

While this study focused on a single module within one discipline, its findings suggest broader applications across higher education. Future research could explore the scalability of this framework to other disciplines, evaluating its impact on diverse student populations and settings. Additionally, further investigation into the long-term career trajectories of graduates could provide valuable insights into the real-world impact of assessment-centered learning frameworks.

One limitation of this study was its reliance on self-reported feedback and performance data from a single institution. Expanding this research to include comparative studies across multiple institutions and disciplines would enhance its generalizability and provide deeper insights into the effectiveness of assessment-centered approaches. Another potential limitation lies in the interpretation of improved grades. While the increase in student performance was significant, it is difficult to entirely attribute these gains to the redesigned assessment. Unpredictable variables, such as fluctuations in student motivation, cohort ability, or external factors, may also have contributed to these improvements.

Furthermore, the study did not include any direct measures to evaluate the adaptability of this assessment framework in preparing students for emerging challenges, such as the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on professional environments. As AI continues to disrupt traditional workflows and skills, future research should investigate whether assessment-centered approaches effectively equip students to navigate these transformations, particularly in areas requiring creativity, critical thinking, and ethical reasoning.

Addressing these limitations and expanding the scope of research could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the potential and adaptability of assessment-centered learning frameworks, ensuring their relevance in an ever-evolving educational and professional landscape.

Conclusion

This study highlights the transformative potential of reimagining assessments as the central element of the learning process, moving away from traditional models that treat assessments as isolated evaluative tools. By implementing a coaching-inspired, open-ended assessment framework that prioritizes autonomy, critical thinking, and real-world application, the CAD module provided a compelling case for how higher education can foster deeper learning and sustained motivation. The integration of career relevance, knowledge connection, and student-centered practices demonstrated how innovative

pedagogical strategies can redefine educational practices to remain competitive and impactful.

The redesign aligned with Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Deci 2000), fostering intrinsic motivation by empowering students to pursue unique solutions tailored to their interests and career goals. This approach was further supported by Connectivism Learning Theory (Siemens 2005), emphasizing the importance of creating networks of knowledge across disciplines. By enabling students to see the real-world implications of their work, the assessment enhanced engagement, knowledge retention, and employability. Graduate feedback reinforced these findings, demonstrating how the assessment cultivated essential lifelong skills, such as adaptability and problem-solving, to navigate the complexities of professional environments.

In addressing the challenges posed by AI disruption, this study underscores the importance of focusing assessments on "how students think" rather than "what they know." By encouraging the synthesis of concepts, creative thinking, and the production of authentic outputs, the assessment safeguarded the relevance of higher education in a rapidly changing technological landscape. This aligns with Brynjolfsson and McAfee's (2014) call for educational practices that prepare students to thrive in digitally enhanced environments by emphasizing critical thinking and adaptability over rote learning.

The motivational impact of the assessment-centered approach was further supported by students' descriptions of the task as "stimulating" and "challenging." These comments reflect the success of creating a student-centered, engaging environment that fosters collaboration, independence, and deep learning. By shifting the focus to a coaching-based framework, the assessment enabled students to expand their zone of proximal development (ZPD) and cultivate both technical and interpersonal skills critical for success in higher education and beyond.

While this study centered on a single intervention—the redesigned CAD assessment—it recognizes the broader role of factors such as lecturer-student partnerships, interdisciplinary connections, and structured feedback in driving the observed improvements (Moore and Kuol 2007). These elements collectively represent a collaborative leadership approach, where educators and students co-create meaningful learning experiences (Harrington et al. 2014). Expanding this model across disciplines and institutions offers the potential for systemic transformation in assessment practices, making education more relevant, inclusive, and sustainable.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates the critical role of innovative, assessment-centered strategies in fostering motivation, deep learning, and sustainability in higher education. By adopting open-ended, coaching-based frameworks that emphasize relevance and adaptability, institutions can prepare students for the demands of a sustainability-focused, AI-enhanced world. As higher education continues to evolve, embracing forward-thinking practices like these will be essential for ensuring institutional relevance, resilience, and the preparation of future leaders equipped to navigate an uncertain and interconnected global landscape.

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